

MATLAB-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) for Data Mining as a Tool for Environment Management

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Abstract : Abstract—The application of data mining to environmental monitoring has become crucial for a number of tasks related to emergency management. Over recent years, many tools have been developed for decision support system (DSS) for emergency management. In this article a graphical user interface (GUI) for environmental monitoring system is presented. This interface allows accomplishing (i) data collection and observation and (ii) extraction for data mining. This tool may be the basis for future development along the line of the open source software paradigm.

Keywords : Data Mining, Environmental data, Mathematical Models, Matlab Graphical User Interface

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